
A COMPARATIVE EVALUATION ON THE PERFORMANCE OF BINARY AND MULTI-CLASS SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINES IN THE ANALYSIS AND CLASSIFICATION OF REMOTELY SENSED SATELLITE DATA

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ABSTRACT

Data mining methods can be applied to extract interesting patterns, functional sequences, models and regular “knowledge” from large databases. In particular, they can be used for understanding data, discovering relationships between data sets, construction of knowledge bases, query optimization, data reorganization, capturing the general data characteristics in a simple and concise manner, etc. Knowledge discovery in databases (KDD) is one such step towards realizing information as a production factor. The primary tasks of data mining in practice are prediction and description. *Prediction* involves using some variables or fields within the database to predict unknown or future values of other variables of interest. *Description* focuses on finding interpretable patterns that describe the data. Support vector machines in the data mining and machine learning context have been in use for decades now in classifying both linear and non-linear data bases using the principle of structural risk minimization. The goal of this study is to present the relevance and study the applicability of binary and multi-class support vector machines in finding optimal separable hyperplanes for spatial data pattern recognition. A comparison on their performance will be made against a PAM clustering centered supervised learning based training algorithms for evaluation. Finally comparisons will also be drawn with the set of archived results obtained from using the same data set with techniques borrowed for neural networks, fuzzy logic/ neural fuzzy systems, a home brew remote sensing software MultiSpec and prior data mining exercises using k-means centered supervised and hierarchical CART centered unsupervised learning algorithms. Probable predictor variable relationships will be mined and their effects on the regression/classification model will be discussed.

Keywords

Remote Sensing, Geo-spatial data, Binary and multi-class SVMs, supervised learning, PLS, ridge regression, robust fitting, PAM etc.

1. Introduction:

Spatial data mining for multi-dimensional pattern recognition has attracted a lot of attention in recent years given the scope of advances the area presents and the restrictions of classical data mining exercises in handling the spatial aspect of these data sets. Various spatial data mining methods have been discussed here with primary focus of adapting learning based trainable support vector machines and their relevance discussed in detail. The problem of fitting response variables to a set of independent/dependent explanatory variables is of keen interest across numerous areas of research. Linear and non-linear regression/classification models that result from such endeavors can be used to understand the variations in a set of dependent variables given a set of independent variables. The models developed hence can be used for diagnostic and predictive purposes. However, in this project we aim at carrying out such a task in a high dimensional data space. Techniques that provide easy and reliable results of fit from using high dimensional or huge data sets are of keen interest to the scientific community. Associated minimization of variance, reduction in bias, estimation of residuals and other such statistical measures provide good diagnostics to the study. The objective of such an endeavor is thus to experiment with the various available regression/classification procedures, test their individual suitability to the given data set, propose better models and seek analytical conclusions from such exercises. Corresponding computational complexities of order of processes, storage, time, cost and speed of execution are thus detrimental.

1.1 What is Geo-spatial Remote Sensing data?

[12] Spatial data is the data related to objects that occupy space. A spatial database stores spatial objects represented by spatial data types and spatial relationships among such objects. Spatial data carries topological and or distance information and it is often organized by spatial indexing structures and accessed by spatial search methods. Some typical examples include: ground based spectrometer data, thermal sensor imagery, LIDAR imagery, RADAR imagery,

MS/HS imagery, IR imagery, photogrammetric imagery and GPS data. Traditional (non-spatial) databases are concerned with only the attributes of objects. They make no explicit distinction between the location of an object and its other attributes. A given spatial database provides for the storage and manipulation of four aspects of its data –

- □ Location component
- □ Topological component
- □ Attribute component
- □ Metadata component

The location component is a record of the position in geographical space that determines where something is and what form it takes. The topological component is a record of the logical relationships between different geographic objects. The attribute component is a record of the characteristics of things that determine what geographic objects represent and what properties they have. The metadata component is a thorough documentation of the contents of the overall database.

1.2 Problems associated with RS Data:

[12] Remote sensing data however suffers from severe disturbances due to noise and data irregularities. These are essentially induced due to the earth’s curvature being spherical while the flight path and plane of motion are assumed regular, ignoring discrepancies caused due to the earth and atmospheric reflections, scattering and transmission of signals from other particles in the atmospheres, signal multi-path phenomena, signal interference with land and air based structures, temperature, air electron content and other such parameters. Overlapping of clusters of data is also a well known problem given the similarities in the spectral signatures of various classes in the study area. Deviation of data samples away from normality, correlation between variables, interaction between factors are some of the data and model based concerns.

1.3 What are SVMs?

The idea of support vector machines hinges on two mathematical operations. Firstly, nonlinear mapping of an input vector into a high-dimensional feature space that is hidden from both the input and output. This is followed by construction of an optimal hyperplane for separating the features discovered above to complete the pattern recognition task. Geometric interpretation of hyperplanes is the decision plane that has the maximum margin or separation from the input patterns. SVM implements the optimal classification rule asymptotically in an efficient manner in relationship to Bayes rule minimizing the misclassification rate

without using conditional expectations or any such complex computations. Thus, the support vector machine can provide a good generalization performance on pattern classification problems despite the fact that it does not incorporate problem domain knowledge. Consider a simple linear 2D problem. Given a training sample $\{(x_i, d_i)\}$ for $i = 1$ to N where x_i is the input pattern for the i^{th} example and d_i is the corresponding desired response or the target output. To begin with we assume that the pattern or class represented by the subset $d_i = +1$ and the pattern represented by $d_i = -1$ are linearly separable. The equation of a decision surface in the form of a hyperplane that does the separation is $w^T x + b = 0$ (adopted from the perceptron learning rule) where w is an adjustable weight vector and b is a bias. A graphical model is seen below. We may thus write:

$$w^T x + b \geq 0 \quad \text{for } d_i = +1$$

$$w^T x + b < 0 \quad \text{for } d_i = -1$$

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

For a given weight vector w and bias b , the separation between the hyperplane defined and the closest data point is called the margin of separation. The goal of the support vector machine is to find the particular hyperplane for which the margin is maximized. Under this condition the decision surface is called the optimal hyperplane as seen below.

Figure 4

Let w_0 and b_0 be the optimal weight and bias values. Correspondingly the optimal hyperplane representing a multi-dimensional linear decision surface in the input space is defined by:
 $w_0^T x + b_0 = 0$.

Therefore the discriminate function is given by:

$g(x) = w_0^T x + b_0$ which gives an algebraic measure of the distance from x to the optimal hyperplane. Define $x = x_p + r w_0 / \|w_0\|$ where x_p is the normal projection of x onto the optimal hyperplane and r is the desired algebraic distance. Since by definition $g(x_p) = 0$ we have -

$$g(x) = w_0^T x + b_0 = r \|w_0\|$$

$$\text{or } r = g(x) / \|w_0\|$$

The issue at hand is to find the parameters w_0 and b_0 for the optimal hyperplane given the training set $\Omega = \{(x_i, d_i)\}$. The particular data points for which the decision rules above are satisfied are called the support vectors and hence the name. In conceptual terms support vectors are those data points that lie closest to the decision surface and are therefore the most difficult to classify. As such they have a direct bearing on the optimum location of the decision surface. Extending this to the quadratic optimization case for finding the optimal hyperplanes we rewrite our equations as:

Given the training sample $\{(x_i, d_i)\}$, find a set of Lagrangian multipliers $\{\alpha_i\}$ for $i = 1$ to N that maximize the objective function

$$Q(\alpha) = \sum \alpha_i - \frac{1}{2} \sum \sum \alpha_i \alpha_j d_i d_j x_i^T x_j \quad \text{for } i = 1 \text{ to } N \text{ and } j = 1 \text{ to } N$$

subject to the constraints $\sum \alpha_i d_i = 0$ and $\alpha_i \geq 0$ for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$.

The weight vector minimizes the cost function $\Phi(w) = \frac{1}{2} w^T w$. Note that the cost function is convex in w and the constraints are linear in w . Following the Kuhn-Tucker dual problem optimization we thus solve for

$$\Phi(w_0) = \min J(w, b_0, \alpha_0) \text{ over } w \quad \text{where } J \text{ is the Lagrangian function.}$$

The optimum weight vectors are given by $w_0 = \sum \alpha_0 d_i x_i$ for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$

And the optimum bias is computed using: $b_0 = 1 - w_0^T x^{(s)}$ for $d^{(s)} = 1$

1.4 Binary vs. MSVMs:

[16] Binary support vector machines (BSVMs) are popular tools for finding a decision rule $\phi(x)$ that will minimize misclassifications between the two cases. The usefulness of BSVMs is partially due to its relationship to the theoretically optimal Bayes Rule, shown by Lin (2002). Lin showed that BSVMs approximate Bayes Rule without requiring estimating or requiring knowledge of the conditional probability $p_y(x) = P(Y = y | X = x)$. Some of the other attempts at extending SVMs to the multicategory case include pair wise classifiers and one-versus-rest classifiers, which both implement the binary SVM multiple times to classify groups; and algorithmic extensions which take into account all variables at the same time. None of these extensions has the same

relationship to Bayes Rule as the original model supplied. The purpose of this paper is to present an extension of support vector machines to multi-category situations without losing the relationship to Bayes Rule.

Extension Theory:

In the original SVM framework, the decision rule, $\phi(\mathbf{x}) = \text{sign}(f(\mathbf{x}))$, where $f(\mathbf{x}) = h(\mathbf{x}) + b$ is found by

minimizing $\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (1 - y_i f(\mathbf{x}_i))_+ + \lambda \|h\|_{H_k}^2$. The second

half of the equation is a tuning parameter which penalizes model complexity which might potentially over fit the model. The first half of the equation is the loss function, penalizing decisions which are misclassified or close to the boundary. Symmetry plays an important role in the loss function. Each y_i is either 1 or -1, so correct classifications will always result in a positive number for $y_i f(\mathbf{x}_i)$. Likewise, wrong classifications produce a negative number. Subtracting $y_i f(\mathbf{x}_i)$ from 1 produces positive numbers when the sample is misclassified, negative numbers when the sample is classified correctly and not within 1 unit of the decision boundary, and numbers between 0 and 1 when the sample is on the outskirts of the decision boundary. Extending this to the multicategory situation works as follows. First, since more decision rules are needed to separate out the k different classes, we change f to $\mathbf{f} = (f_1, \dots, f_k)$. The class codes, y_i are also extended to vector form, specifically when y belongs to the j^{th} class, we take $\mathbf{y}_i = \mathbf{v}_j = (\frac{-1}{k-1}, \dots, \frac{-1}{k-1}, 1, \frac{-1}{k-1}, \dots, \frac{-1}{k-1})$, where 1 occurs in the j^{th} coordinate. Note that the sum of the coordinates in \mathbf{y} is 0. This preserves the symmetry of -1 and 1 from the binary case. Likewise,

we choose $\sum_{i=1}^k f_j(\mathbf{x}) = 0$. By taking the inner product of

$(\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_i) - \mathbf{y}_i)$ and a vector representing the cost of misclassifying class j into class ℓ , we get a new measure of the loss function which corresponds directly to the weight of a boundary line point in the original SVM. Continuing in this manner, it can be shown that $\{L(\mathbf{y}_i) \cdot (\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_i) - \mathbf{y}_i)_+\}$ produces analogous results as $[(1 - y_i f(\mathbf{x}_i))_+]$ in the binary case. Furthermore, the proofs showing the relationship between binary SVMs and Bayes Rule can be extended to the multicategory case, thus linking this extension of support vector machines to the optimal decision rule. The MSVM solution closely follows the target results derived from Bayes Rule. Thus, the simulation suggests that implementation of MSVM keeps the desired properties. In the binary case, we seek a decision rule.

It has been shown that

$$\min \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n L(\mathbf{y}_i) \cdot (\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_i) - \mathbf{y}_i)_+ + \frac{1}{2} \lambda \sum_{j=1}^k \|h_j\|_{H_k}^2$$

approximates Bayes Rule without estimating the conditional probability function. The exact value of $f(x)$ is related to the distance from the line separating the two classes. They allow formulations under both equal and unequal cost misclassification structures, help design a target oriented loss function that maximizes the conditionals probability, works to find an optimum trade off between the model complexity through the penalty function and model loss function accounting for the biases and variance, and adapts well to any tuning measure. On proper adjustments the desirable properties of binary SVMs can be extended fruitfully to MSVMs.

1.5 Why SVMs in RS data analysis and classification?

When performing pattern recognition task, the support vector learning algorithm minimizes the number of training samples that fall inside the margin of separation between positive and negative examples. While analogous to that of minimization of misclassification error it is considered to be more appropriate than the mean square or lest square error criterion usually observed in other optimization and classification methods. Further when performing any nonlinear regression or classification task, the algorithm minimizes the loss function that is an extension of the mean absolute error criterion of the minimax theory thus making it more robust. It provides a method for controlling model complexity independently of dimensionality. The result is a good generalization performance. The curse of dimensionality is bypassed by focusing on the dual problem for performing the constrained optimization problem. The algorithm is guaranteed to find a global extremum of the error surface and this computation can be performed very efficiently. The SVM machine is itself used as a nonlinear regression and classification tool to approximate the decision surface and hyperplanes with a user-specified accuracy. The procedure for training support vector machines is reformulated to yield the same exact decision surface while using a smaller number of basis functions. Using additional terms in the cost function allows the learning machine to construct a function that incorporates prior knowledge which is the use of regularization. As the name implies, the design of the machine hinges on the extraction of a subset of the training data that serves as support vectors and therefore represents a stable characteristic of the data. It has been claimed and proven that this method has the

potential of yielding a significant gain in spatial data classification accuracy at a moderate cost in time.

1.6 Data Description:

The data obtained was a multi-spectral RGB color coded image of an agricultural land mass in north central Indiana. The data was recorded and stored as flight line FIC1.lan.

Table 1: Image Description from MultiSpec

Description information for: 'FLC1.LAN'	
File format:	Erdas73
Image type:	Multispectral
Band interleave format:	BIL
Signed data:	No
Number of lines:	949
Number of columns:	220
Number of channels:	12
Number of bytes:	1
Number of bits:	8
Number of header bytes:	128
Number of pre-line bytes:	0
Number of post-line bytes:	0
Number of pre-channel bytes:	0
Number of post-channel bytes:	0
Line start:	1
Column start:	1

2. Related Work:

[16] Yoonkyung Lee, Yi Lin, and Grace Wahba in their work on the cloud classification with radiance profiles found that MSVM approach performs better than both the 1-NN and tree based classification methods which highlight the relevance of MSVMs as a useful classification tool for remotely sensed data given its ability of generating and operating with optimal tuning parameters, loss functions and misclassification rates. MODIS (moderate resolution imaging spectroradiometer) measures radiances at 36 different wavelengths (channels) used in Earth Observing System (EOS) models. EOS models require knowledge of whether a radiance profile is cloud free, or not. If the profile isn't cloud free, it is useful to know what type of cloud it contains. Simulated MODIS data was generated from different atmospheric conditions, and the MSVM approach was used to classify each of 744 observations as clear skies, ice clouds, or liquid clouds. 7 reflectances (R) and 5 brightness temperatures (BT) were collected for each data point. No single channel gives a clear separation (the graph shows RChannel 2 against $\log_{10}(R_{Channel 5}/R_{Channel 6})$ as an example. The data set was randomly divided into a training set of

370 samples and a test set of 374 samples. Training was performed using four different combinations of variables, namely 2 using prior knowledge of physics to find optimal combinations and 2 using all 12 variables (raw and log transformed). MSVM used the Gaussian kernel and 5-fold cross validation was used to tune parameters. On careful observation of the example it is noted that moving from two to five variables does not significantly decrease the misclassification rate. Worst results come from using all of the twelve original variables. Further, best results come from using all 12 log-transformed variables which suggest that even for non-Gaussian data where data transformation is warranted, MSVMs outperform other algorithms. Specific to the example, it is seen that most classification problems occur where clear and ice clouds appear to overlap. Misclassifying clouds as clear being more serious than other misclassifications is the motivation behind altering the cost matrix to suit the user defined classification requirements. This adaptive nature of the SVMs is of particular interest to the scientific community.

Figure 5

Most classification problems occur where clear and ice clouds appear to overlap. Misclassifying clouds as clear is more serious than other misclassifications. What if we changed the cost matrix?

Figure 6 Left: standard case. Right: adjusted cost matrix.

3. Data Cleaning:

Data cleaning was undertaken as a prior tool to make the data refined enough for feeding into the final clustering and classification algorithms for both the SVM and supervised cases. This ensured that non-normal high-bias high-variance non-linear data was regularized and data more uniform for more accurate and reliable interpretations. The problem of data cleaning as envisioned was multifold. The following exercises were carried out as part of the process.

- Checking of normality assumptions through histogram plot (subsequent data transformation if required)
- Error testing and Residual analysis through qq-plot and normal quantile plot
- Correlation and interaction tests using correlation and interaction plots
- Outlier detection through regression analysis
- Feature selection using ridge regression and robust fit
- Feature extraction using derived inputs models based partial least squares method

3.1 Checking of normality assumptions:

This was done by constructing the histogram plot and superimposing the Gaussian kernel over the vector bars. This followed from the initial assumption that the data was large enough in terms of size and dimensionality to enforce the central limit theorem which pushed the samples to Gaussian behavior.

Figure 7

Figure 8

3.2 Error testing and Residual analysis:

Standard regression based least square errors and residuals were obtained from a linear regression model that was fitted to accommodate all the data points. Corresponding plots were as seen below.

Figure 9

Figure 10

From the qq – plot, the residual plot and the normal quantile plot above, it has been noted that the assumption of data being pretty much normally distributed is slightly violated with the presence of

wiggles towards the right tail region which thus does warranty the requirement of a transformation. However assumptions of constant variance, normality of errors and independent data (error) samples hold.

Table 2

Transformation Information
for Box-Cox(corn)

Lambda	R-Square	Log Like
-2.0	0.92	-792.651
-1.8	0.92	-741.180
-1.6	0.92	-690.649
-1.4	0.92	-641.303
-1.2	0.92	-593.492
-1.0	0.92	-547.719
-0.8	0.92	-504.731
-0.6	0.92	-465.620
-0.4	0.92	-431.926
-0.2	0.91	-405.618
0.0	0.91	-388.770
0.2	0.90	-382.821 <
0.4	0.90	-387.751
0.6	0.90	-401.975
0.8	0.90	-423.189
1.0	0.90	-449.290
1.2	0.90	-478.743
1.4	0.90	-510.538
1.6	0.90	-544.022
1.8	0.90	-578.773
2.0	0.90	-614.506

< - Best Lambda
* - Confidence Interval
+ - Convenient Lambda

Continuing from the result of the box-cox data transformation all the data vectors were raised to a power of 0.2.

3.3 Correlation and Interaction tests:

We see from the plotted LS regression coefficients β and correlation coefficients γ , that most of the predictor variables are uncorrelated and independent. This adheres to the model assumptions that were made prior to the execution of the project. However, a few predictor variables are found to be slightly correlated and dependent as seen below. The max value of γ obtained was 0.15 and that of β was 0.4. While these values are small they are still noted to be significant enough to influence the regression/classification procedures listed

above. The statistical methods adapted above looks the best choice of algorithms in such cases where predictor variables are slightly correlated, given their ability to take care of partial correlation through significance tests. This is because of the fact that both ridge & robust regression assumed that the data is redundant and suffers from multi-co linearity which might be the case in this data set that drives the $X^T X$ matrix to singularity. The same argument can be put forth in favor of the PLS based derived inputs regression/classification. These might be the reasons for the aforementioned procedures performing well with the data set although marginal cases of correlation, redundancy, multi-co linearity and dependence were detected.

Figure 11

Figure 12

From the correlation plot we do not observe any inter-dependence or inter-variability between predictor variables. However, from the interaction plot we do observe interaction between the relevant factors.

3.4 Outlier detection through regression analysis:

The linear model takes its common form:

$$Y = X\beta + \varepsilon$$

where: Y is an n -by-1 vector of observations. X is an n -by- p matrix of regressors. β is a p -by-1 vector of parameters. ε is an n -by-1 vector of random disturbances. The solution to the problem is a vector, b , which estimates the unknown vector of parameters. The least squares solution is:

$$\hat{\beta} = (X^T X)^{-1} X^T Y$$

You can plug b back into the model formula to get the predicted y values at the data points.

$$Y^{\wedge} = X\hat{\beta}$$

Statisticians use a hat (circumflex) over a letter to denote an estimate of a parameter or a prediction from a model. The projection matrix H is called the hat matrix, because it puts the "hat" on Y .

$$H = X(X^T X)^{-1} X^T Y$$

The residuals are the difference between the observed and predicted Y values.

$$\varepsilon = Y - Y^{\wedge}$$

The residuals are useful for detecting failures in the model assumptions, since they correspond to the errors, in the model equation. By assumption, these errors each have independent normal distributions with mean zero and a constant variance.

Figure 13

From the regression analysis, we do observe the presence of outliers in the data set as seen from the plot above. The outliers have been retained assuming that they have strong statistical significance to the analysis process and are hence worth including in the study.

3.5 Feature selection using ridge regression and robust fit:

Shrinkage estimation derives its name from the fact that there is an overall reduction in the variance at the cost of small bias. Two popular methods employed in the shrinkage estimation method are:

- Lasso method
- Ridge regression

In this exercise we explore the ridge regression approach.

3.5a Ridge Regression:

The original motivation for this technique is that $X^T X$ being close to singular leads to unstable parameter estimation and increase in the subsequent variance which the ridge method tries to counter. The underlying assumption in this process is the response will vary most in the directions of high variance of inputs which is reasonable but not always true. The algorithm for the ridge regression procedure is as follows:

$$\sum_{i=1}^p \text{Var}(b_i) = \text{MSE}(b) = E\{(b-\beta)^T(b-\beta)\} = \sigma^2 \sum_{i=1}^p \lambda_i^{-1}$$

where λ_i = the i^{th} Eigen value of $X^T X$ matrix

if $X^T X$ is singular $\lambda_i \approx 0$

$$\hat{\beta}^{\text{ridge}} = \underset{\beta}{\text{argmin}} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \beta_0 - \sum_{j=1}^p X_{ij} \beta_j)^2 + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j^2 \right\}$$

where $\lambda > 0$ is called the complexity parameters which controls the amount of shrinkage

$$\rightarrow \hat{\beta}^{\text{ridge}} = \underset{\beta}{\text{argmin}} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \beta_0 - \sum_{j=1}^p X_{ij} \beta_j)^2 \right\}$$

$$\text{Subject to } \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j^2 \leq S$$

for the given data set of Y and X 's, $\hat{\beta}^{\text{ridge}}$ is computed using:

$\hat{\beta}^{\text{ridge}} = (X^T X + kI)^{-1} X^T Y$ which is analogous to the LS estimator of $\hat{\beta}^{\text{ridge}} = (X^T X)^{-1} X^T Y$, the additional component taking care of the shrinkage.

Ridge regression shrinks the variance along the to main principal component directions the most and fits a linear space over the area that encompasses the two main PCs (the smallest and the largest). It protects

against the potentially high variance of gradients estimated in the short direction.

Figure 16

Figure 17

3.5b Robust Fit:

We found an outlier when we used ordinary least squares regression to model a response as a function of five predictors. How did that outlier affect the results? It is helpful to look at the weight variable from the robust fit. It measures how much weight was given to each point during the fit. In this case, the points having a very low weight were effectively ignored. The robust function presents a simple comparison of least squares and robust fits for a response and a single predictor. The effect of any point on the least squares fit depends on the residual and leverage for that point. The residual is simply the vertical distance from the point to the line. The leverage is a measure of how far the point is from the center of the X data. The effect of any point on the robust fit also depends on the weight assigned to the point. Points far from the line get lower weight.

The algorithm for the robust fit regression is as follows:

The robust fit function estimates the variance-covariance matrix of the coefficient estimates as $V = \text{inv}(X^T * X) * \text{stats}.s^2$. The standard errors and correlations are derived from V. b, the vector of estimated parameters uses robust regression to fit Y as a function of the columns of X, and returns the vector b of coefficient estimates. The robust fit function uses an iteratively reweighted least squares algorithm, with the weights at each iteration calculated by applying the bisquare function to the residuals from the previous iteration. This algorithm gives lower weight to points that do not fit well. The results are less sensitive to outliers in the data as compared with ordinary least squares regression. The value r in the weight function expression is equal to $\text{resid}/(\text{tune} * s * \text{sqrt}(1-h))$ where resid is the vector of residuals from the previous iteration, tune is the tuning constant, h is the vector of leverage values from a least squares fit, and s is an estimate of the standard deviation of the error term given by $s = \text{MAD}/0.6745$. The quantity MAD is the median absolute deviation of the residuals from their median. The constant 0.6745 makes the estimate unbiased for the normal distribution. If there are p columns in the X matrix (including the constant term, if any), the smallest p-1 absolute deviations are excluded when computing their median. The argument tune overrides the default tuning constant from the table. A smaller tuning constant tends to down weight large residuals more severely, and a larger tuning constant down weights large residuals less severely. The default tuning constants yield coefficient estimates that are approximately 95% as efficient as least squares estimates, when the response has a normal distribution with no outliers. As an alternative to specifying one of the named weight functions, one can write their own weight function that takes a vector of scaled residuals as input and produces a vector of weights as output.

Robust regression in combination with ridge fit might thus be better than the procedures used earlier given its ability to detect outliers and weigh the samples in the basis of their influence on the dataset and in determining the response variable Y. This leads to greater weights for more significant variables, the idea of which is analogous to the PC based method. However we do not exclude the insignificant variables but only account for their effect by using a reduced weight. Further as the outlier detection procedure here involves taking into account the auto and cross correlation values, significance tests results from such an exercise have found to be very useful. As the fit is more robust and iterative, a most accurate variance shrinkage factor is used for the final fit of the model. In summary, all the advantages of the regression

procedures, ridge, stepwise and PC based method have been incorporated in one technique and hence my assumption that this method would be ideal for spatial data sets of such kind.

Figure 18

3.6 Feature extraction using derived inputs model based partial least squares method:

The LS procedure fits models using any one of a number of linear predictive methods, including partial least squares (PLS). Ordinary least squares regression, has the single goal of minimizing sample response prediction error, seeking linear functions of the predictors that explain as much variation in each response as possible. The techniques implemented in the PLS procedure have the additional goal of accounting for variation in the predictors, under the assumption that directions in the predictor space that are well sampled should provide better prediction for new observations when the predictors are highly correlated. All of the techniques implemented in the PLS procedure work by extracting successive linear combinations of the predictors, called factors (also called components or latent vectors), which optimally address one or both of these two goals -explaining response variation and explaining predictor variation. In particular, the method of PLS balances the two objectives, seeking for factors that explain both response and predictor variation. However, the PLS procedure fits only predictive PLS models, with one "block" of predictors and one "block" of responses. This technique constructs a set of linear combinations of the inputs for regression. Since it uses the response to construct its directions, its solutions is a nonlinear function of the response.. PLS seeks directions that have high variance and high correlation with the response in contrast to principal component regressions. The mth PLS direction ϕ_m^{\wedge} solves:

$$\max \text{Corr}^2(y, X\alpha) \text{Var}(X\alpha)$$

$$\|\alpha\| = 1$$

$$\phi_1^T S \alpha = 0 \text{ for } l =$$

1,2,.....,m-1

where y = response and X α = the std input vectors

further analysis reveals that the variance aspects tends to dominate and so PLS behaves much like ridge regression and PC regression. The sequence of PLS coefficients for m = 1,2,.....,p represents the conjugate gradient sequence for computing the least squares solution.

The algorithm is given by:

Step 1: standardize each input vector to have zero mean and variance one.

Step 2: set $y^{\wedge}(0) = 1.y$ and $x_j(0) = x_j$ for j = 1,2,.....,p

Step 3: for m = 1,2,.....,p

- $z_m = \sum \phi_{mj}^{\wedge} x_j(m-1)$ where $\phi_{mj}^{\wedge} = \langle x_j(m-1), y \rangle / \langle z_m, z_m \rangle$ for j = 1,2,.....,p
- $\theta_m^{\wedge} = \langle z_m, y \rangle / \langle z_m, z_m \rangle$
- $y^{\wedge}(m) = y^{\wedge}(m-1) + \theta_m^{\wedge} * z_m$
- orthogonalise each $x_j(m-1)$ with respect to z_m using:

$$x_j(m) = x_j(m-1) - [\langle z_m, x_j(m-1) \rangle / \langle z_m, z_m \rangle] z_m \text{ for } j = 1,2,.....,p$$

Step 4: output the sequence of fitted vectors $\{y^{\wedge}(m)\}$ from 1 to p. Since the $\{z_j\}$ from 1 to m are linear in the original x_j , so is $y^{\wedge}(m) = X\beta_{pls}^{\wedge}(m)$. These linear coefficients can be recovered fro the sequence of PLS transformations.

Blocked Cross Validation for the Number of Extracted Factors

Number of Extracted Factors	Root Mean PRESS
0	1.013333
1	0.825565
2	0.803786
3	0.793387

4 0.78859
 5 0.789672
 6 0.794663
 7 0.79001

0.7886 Minimum root mean PRESS
 Minimizing number of factors 4

Percent Variation Accounted for by Partial Least Squares Factors

Number of Extracted Factors	Model Effects			
	roadways waterbody alphaalpha	railways wheat	redclover Current	soybean
1	18.6890	0.2041	13.9315	71.2460
2.5968	7.1772	84.5027	28.3353	
2	89.1055	46.5493	69.5646	71.6095
74.5766	90.9196	87.6704	47.3783	
3	90.6930	81.0869	79.6718	76.1706
86.2874	97.0933	92.6500	10.5225	
4	93.6849	85.8007	94.7647	98.4288
89.3232	97.6019	99.2094	7.8801	

Percent Variation Accounted for by Partial Least Squares Factors

Variables Total	Number of Extracted Factors	Model Effects Total	Dependent	
			corn	Current
	1	28.3353	35.7678	35.7678
35.7678	2	75.7136	39.5142	3.7464
39.5142	3	86.2361	41.8075	2.2933
41.8075	4	94.1162	42.1022	0.2947
42.1022				

From the statistics above we observe that the number of extracted factors being 4 the percentage variation explained is around 90% for each of the class vectors. This confirms the initial hypothesis obtained on reconnaissance that corn, wheat, soybean and red clover are statistically the most dominate classes in the study area.

3.6a Cross Validation:

One of the criteria that were adopted for model selection and prediction error estimates was the cross-validation technique which is basically an unbiased estimate of the expected loss in fitting given a set of response and fitted response variables. It was also used as a measure of statistical accuracy of the two aforementioned regression procedures and hence ended up being a tool for comparative study and assessment. The algorithm of the CV technique is as follows:

Step 1: Randomly partition the data into N partitions of equal size

Step 2: For i = 1 to N use U Pj as a training set given i ≠ j → use all but the ith partition

Estimate f[^] -1 based on (N-1)/N % of data where f[^] is the function of fitted response values

Step 3: Calculate the prediction error PE using the ith partition for the loss function

$$PE = L_i = 1/|p_i| \sum L\{y_{is}, f^{\wedge} -1(X_j)\} \text{ for } j \in P_i$$

where |p_i| = the number of observations in partition p_i = size of p_i = cardinality of p_i

Step 4: Cross validation estimate is computed using the relation:

$$CV = 1/N \sum_{i=1}^N L_i$$

Using the hold-out or the leave-one-out notation

$$\rightarrow CV = 1/N \sum_{i=1}^N L\{y_{is}, f^{\wedge} -1(X_i), \alpha\}$$

where α = the tuning parameter such that:

$$\alpha^* = \operatorname{argmin}_{\alpha} CV(\alpha) = \min PE = \min L_i$$

NOTE: The training to test data set ratio in this exercise was 70%-30%. This was an approximation from observing the average CV values for all procedures.

Figure 19

The plot above suggests that the LOO-CV procedure when applied to the ridge regression coefficients obtained the number of clusters as 5 = (4+1) for which the residual variance and hence the predicted error is the least. The interpretation of this result would be that the effect of clusters pertaining to alpha-alpha, water body and railways classes are not statistically significant. Further effect of outliers on the data set is also marginal which reinforces our earlier conclusion from the regression analysis.

4. Supervised Learning:

As the name suggests supervised learning deals with data based modeling and learning with pre-specified user-defined accuracies and target outputs. The user in this process has greater control over the training and simulation aspects of the learning algorithms given a pre-determined set of desired response values which are quantified into the algorithm as error terms by measuring their deviation away from the actual outputs.

4.1 Clustering using PAM:

Partitioning (clustering) of the data into k clusters around “medoids”, is a more robust version of k-means. Compared to the k-means approach in k-means, the function ‘pam’ has the following features: (a) it also accepts a dissimilarity matrix; (b) it is more robust because it minimizes a sum of dissimilarities instead of a sum of squared Euclidean distances. The PAM-algorithm is based on the search for ‘k’ representative objects or medoids among the observations of the dataset. These observations should represent the structure of the data. After finding a set of k medoids, k clusters are constructed by assigning each observation to the nearest medoid. The goal is to find k representative objects which minimize the sum of the dissimilarities of the observations to their closest representative object. The algorithm first looks for a

good initial set of medoids (this is called the build phase). Then it finds a local minimum for the objective function, that is, a solution such that there is no single switch of an observation with a medoid that will decrease the objective (this is called the swap phase). The essential differences with k-means are that PAM needs only pair wise distance matrix unlike k-means which needs to use all data points to compute the distance matrix and finally PAM is more computationally intensive than k-means. The algorithm is given by:

Step 1: let $D(X_i, X_{i'}) = \sum_{j=1}^p |X_{ij} - X_{ij'}|$ for some input patterns X_i and class j

Step 2: choose an objective function that minimizes the sum of within-cluster distances.

Step 3: given cluster assignment C, find observations in the cluster minimizing the total distance to other points in that cluster using –

$$i_k^* = \operatorname{argmin}_{\{i: (i) = k\}} \sum_{i'} d(X_i, X_{i'}) \quad C(i') = k$$

$$\rightarrow m_k = X_{i_k^*} \quad \text{for } k = 1, 2, \dots, k;$$

Note: cluster center = medoid

Given (m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k) assign each observation to the closest cluster center.

$$C(i) = \operatorname{argmin}_{i \leq k \leq K} d(X_i, m_k) \text{ for } K \text{ medoids}$$

Step 4: iterate the last two functions listed in step 3 until the assignments do not change.

Figure 20

Figure 22
Scatter plot of the final clusters for data set

Figure 21

These silhouette plots indicate that these are probably the right number of clusters, since all the clusters contain points with mostly high silhouette values. However, without some knowledge of how many clusters are really in the data, it is a good idea to experiment with a range of values for k.

4.2 Bayesian Classification:

In the Bayes classifier algorithm also known as the Bayes hypothesis testing procedure, the average risk is minimized to yield the optimal linear classification boundary. The algorithm is given by:

Assuming an 8-class Gaussian distributed problem the following equations hold:

$$Y = w^T X + b$$

where

$$Y = \text{linear classifier} = \log \Lambda(X)$$

for

X = the source or the input data vector

w = the weight vector = $C^{-1}(\mu_1 - \mu_2, \dots)$

b = the bias vector = $\frac{1}{2}(\mu_2^T C^{-1} \mu_2 - \mu_1^T C^{-1} \mu_1 \dots)$

for a covariance matrix $C = E[(X-\mu)(X-\mu)^T]$

Figure 23

Figure 24

5. SVM Learning:

Prior to executing the training, learning, simulation and classification exercises within the SVM domain the Gap statistic was employed to find the optimal number of clusters in the data set.

5.1 Cluster estimation using Gap statistic:

Idea: Suppose there are actually k^* distinct groups of the observations.

Case 1: $k < k^* \rightarrow W_{k+1} \ll W_k$

Case 2: $k > k^*$

k^* is obtained by identifying a “kink” in the plot of W_k as a function of k .

where W_k = within-point-scatter

Theory: consider data $X_{ij}, i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$

$J = 1, 2, 3, \dots, p$

which is a p -dimensional data set with n observations

Let $d_{ii} = d(X_i, X_i) = \sum (X_{ij} - X_{ij})^2 = \text{Euclidean distance metric for } j = 1 \text{ to } p$

Suppose for k clusters, $C_1, C_2, C_3, \dots, C_k$

Let $n_r = |C_r|$: number of observations in cluster r

let $D_r = \sum_{i, i' \in r} d_{ii'}$: sum of all pair wise distances

$W_k = \sum_{r=1}^k (1/2n_r) D_r$: pooled sum of within dissimilarity

If d is squared Euclidean distance

W_k = pooled within cluster SS around the means

Gap Statistic = $G(k) = E^* \{ \log(W_k) \} - \log(W_k)$

Where E^* = expectation from the reference distribution

Motivation: Find k the maximizes Gap $G(k)$.

Algorithm:

Step 1: Cluster the observed data; change the number of clusters

$k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, K$

Step 2: Compute W_k for $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, K$

Step 3: Generate B reference data sets uniform in the range of the observed values

Step 4: Compute W_{bb}^*

$k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, K$: number of clusters

$b = 1, 2, 3, \dots, B$: number of data sets

Compute $\text{gap}(k) = 1/B \sum_{b=1}^B \log(W_{kb}^*) - \log(W_k)$

Step 5: let $\hat{I} = 1/B \sum_{b=1}^B \log(W_{kb}^*)$

Standard deviation $sd_k = \sqrt{1/B \sum_b [\log(W_{kb}^*) - \hat{I}]^2}$

Step 6; $s_k = sd_k \sqrt{1 + 1/B}$

Step 7: choose $\hat{k} = \text{argmin} \{ k: \text{Gap}(k) \geq \text{Gap}(k-1) - s_{k+1} \}$

k

→ Compare $\log(W_k)$ from data to $\log(W_k)$ from uniformly distributed data over a rectangle

→ Optimal number of clusters = where the “gap” between the two curves on the $\log(W_k)$ vs. k plot is the highest

From the plots below we observe that our initial assumption that the data set contains eight clusters is validated.

Figure 25

Figure 26

5.2 SVM Classification:

The following plots were obtained on using the binary and multi-class support vector machines as final classification results. Note that the decision boundaries were well defined for the 2 and 4-class problems but a regular hyperplane separating the multi-class input patterns was not very convincing. A default radial basis function kernel with parameters (γ, σ^2) was assumed given the Gaussian assumption of the data distribution where gamma was the regularization parameter,

determining the trade-off between the fitting error minimization and smoothness and σ^2 is the bandwidth. We do observe that on effective training and simulation the true and resultant final class labels perfectly matched and were as expected.

Figure 27

Figure 28

Figure 29

Figure 30

6. Experimental Results:

An intrinsic comparison was made on the performance of SVMs with supervised learning and MultiSpec software methods. The parameter used for this comparison was the classification accuracy of the training set relative to a test set that was retained common in all methods. A comparison of this nature is validated from the fact that we have established the close relationship between Binary/MSVM classification to that of Bayes' classification based on objective (cost) function minimization. While the Bayesian approach was the end classification problem in the supervised learning problem, it was a similar approach that was employed in the MultiSpec software.

6.1 Supervised vs. SVM learning:

SVMs outperformed standard machine learning-data mining based supervised and unsupervised learning methods. The reason attributed to this difference in performance is the process through which SVMs perform the objective function minimization by following a penalty method. This forces additional constraints on the data driven algorithms which then is better suited for adaptability and learning given the fact that the errors and residuals are within permissible limits. Further, it has been noted that SVM deviate slightly from the Bayesian approach by not relying on complex conditional expectations and their associated costs which might sometimes are known to be biased. MSVMs work well under quadratic programming based non-linear constrained optimization that approximates the required parameters and variables better. SVMs also provide a medium to fine tune the learning parameters to the optimum value while penalizing model complexities and addressing problems associated with high-dimensionalities that classical data mining methods do not address. The SVM pattern classifiers are unique due to their promising generalization performance. The mathematical formulation of SVMs embodies the Structural Risk Minimization (SRM) principle, as opposed to the Empirical Risk Minimization (ERM) approach commonly employed within statistical learning methods. It is this difference which equips SVMs with an excellent potential to generalize.

6.2 SVMs vs. MultiSpec:

[13] On using the MultiSpec software, obtained training accuracy was of the order of **86.4%** while the predetermined test accuracy was in the range of **75- 85%** for the end classification statistic. In this procedure the conventional pattern recognition methods including feature selection using mean Bhattacharya distance metric, decision boundary feature extraction, ISODATA statistical clustering with Bayesian classification were used. SVMs outperformed MultiSpec considerably using the GAP cluster statistics. The reasons behind this marked improvement in the accuracy of training class data are attributed to the prior data cleaning process that was done which was pretty much missing in the MultiSpec system and the learning-adapting-simulating-training-testing format of the SVM system which forces the errors of misclassification to be as close to zero as possible.

7. Comparison with archived results:

Table 3

Method	Algorithms	Training class accuracy
MultiSpec	Bhatta dist FS, dbFE, isodata, Bayes	~ 86.40%
Supervised Learning	K-means, EM and Bayes	~ 97.81%
Unsupervised Learning	CART, bootstrapping, Bayes	
Neural Networks	Backprop, AVQ, Adaline, SOM, LVQ etc	~ 98.02%
Fuzzy Logic and Neural Fuzzy Systems	Sub-clustering, fuzzy C – means	~ 96.02%
Supervised Learning	PAM, Bayes	~ 96.56%
Binary and MSVM	Gap, multilayer perceptron	~ 98.43%

8. Conclusions and Inferences:

[12] Learning algorithm based machine learning and data mining techniques showed on an average, better results in terms of accuracy as these procedures work on the principle of error minimization. The second advantage with these procedures was the minimization of biases by randomizing the data. These algorithms helped capture non-linearity to a greater extent and most end results after simulation plotted linear classified data points. Scaling, over-fitting the data, temporal changes in the variables, occurrence of local minima, over shooting the desired optimum and other such algorithm related problems did not surface when using the data mining methods indicating superior adaptivity, greater robust nature of the programs and hence more accurate learning. Finally the ML/DM accounted comparatively much better when it came to modeling noisy data and data irregularities. While SVMs worked as well as traditional data mining techniques in terms of the performance parameters listed above, they were seen to be the most ideally suited for mapping noisy non-Gaussian data to final linear and non-linear classification regions. The adaptability of SVMs to spatial data sets in understanding and incorporating the space component in the final analysis is note worthy in comparison to classical machine learning methods. Their suitability to spatial data analysis is further enriched by the fact that SVMs are kernel based data driven models which provide better classification results as seen from the results above. This exercise has helped me understand the relevance and usefulness in the techniques of machine learning, knowledge discovery, data mining and related support vector machine learning in the study of geo-spatial data for the purposes of analysis, classification and prediction. It has been noted that these techniques were superior to the conventional existing techniques in some areas like in capturing the non – linearity in the data and error minimization. While on the other hand conventional techniques like the maximum likelihood classifier in combination with the decision boundary feature extraction performed with superior accuracy when the data was linear and well distributed.

9. Future work:

It is proposed to extend this study to the analysis and classification of hyper-spectral, thermal, infrared, RADAR and LIDAR imagery so as to achieve maximum and optimal data classification and information extraction. Effect of these image (data) collection methods on the algorithms employed and vice-versa will be investigated. For example, thermal and IR imagery are collected in the middle & far IR and

thermal regions of the EM spectrum while RADAR and LIDAR data correspond to the microwave and laser regions. Effects and properties of these regions from a physical and statistical standpoint are of keen interest with respect to final data classification using ML/DM methods. [12] Also, a query based spatial data base development using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) technology, integrating with Global Positioning Systems (GPS) and bi-static RADAR sources to determine the Z-dimension, time series based statistical modeling & analysis and applying statistical space inference methods would be interesting follows on the project. In conclusion, archiving the results obtained from using MultiSpec, neural networks, fuzzy logic systems, neural fuzzy systems, machine learning & data mining and SVM techniques on the same data set is possible. [12] Testing the relevance and applicability of other useful methods from the areas of digital image processing, biologically inspired genetic algorithms and scientific data visualization for analysis is noteworthy and warrants attention from a research standpoint.

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